

TENSILE CYCLIC BEHAVIOR OF OPEN-HOLE CFRP LAMINATES WITH ULTRA-THIN PLYS

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of *scale effect* in composite materials is defined by reduced damage onset associated with a decrease in ply thickness. This effect has garnered renewed interest with the advent of low-grammage prepregs, prompting an upsurge in research into the use of ultra-thin plies in composite laminate manufacturing. In this regard, previous studies have primarily concentrated on the effects of the use of ultra-thin plies in the case of cross-ply laminates subjected to cyclic tensile loads.

Given this context, the present experimental study explores the integration of ultra-thin plies in multidirectional CFRP composite laminates, specifically in open-hole configurations, to assess damage evolution under tension-tension fatigue. The analysis compares quasi-isotropic laminates consisting of conventional thickness plies with their equivalent versions incorporating 90° ultra-thin plies, maintaining the same stacking sequences. Additionally, two distinct stacking sequences are investigated. The primary objective is to assess the impact of 90° ultra-thin plies and their distribution through the laminate thickness on damage evolution, aiming to identify potential improvements in laminate performance.

Following quasi-static tensile characterisation, the open-hole specimens are subjected to tension-tension fatigue testing with a stress ratio of $R=0.1$, where the maximum stress represents a fraction of the ultimate tensile strength. Damage onset and progression during cyclic loading are monitored using ultrasonic inspection. The results demonstrate that laminates with ultra-thin plies exhibit slower damage evolution and reduced sensitivity to the presence of the open hole at equivalent load levels. Moreover, the findings underscore the critical role of stacking sequence reorganization, particularly in mitigating free-edge damage mechanisms.

These observations suggest that multidirectional laminates featuring ultra-thin plies deliver superior performance under tensile fatigue loading. The results support their potential for enhanced structural durability, reinforcing the viability of implementing ultra-thin ply technology at an industrial scale.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent interest in understanding the so-called *scale effect* [1] has driven growing research on the use of ultra-thin plies in the fabrication of composite laminates. Several studies have examined how these plies influence the performance of cross-ply laminates subjected to cyclic tensile loading [2]. Findings consistently show that the damage mechanisms in 90° plies vary significantly depending on whether the plies are of conventional or ultra-thin thickness, with the latter delaying damage initiation and leading to a less severe onset of degradation.

Following the approach of these previous studies, the present study explores whether incorporating ultra-thin plies can enhance the mechanical response of quasi-isotropic laminates. In particular, it focuses on open-hole carbon fibre/epoxy laminates [3], comparing configurations made entirely with conventional plies to those where only the 90° plies are replaced by ultra-thin plies.

In this regard, previous investigations into open-hole quasi-isotropic specimens have primarily examined how ply thickness influences mechanical performance under quasi-static [4–7] and cyclic tensile loading [8–9]. For instance, in [9], tension–tension fatigue tests compared laminates made with thin, intermediate, and thick plies—where all plies were uniformly scaled in thickness—focusing on stiffness degradation and internal damage evolution via X-ray radiography.

In contrast, the present work adopts a different strategy. Two laminate configurations with identical stacking sequences were designed: one composed entirely of conventional plies, and another where only the 90° plies were substituted with ultra-thin plies. Both configurations were tested using two distinct stacking sequences, ensuring identical proportions of 0°, ±45°, and 90° orientations. Following specimen fabrication, cyclic tensile tests were performed on open-hole samples to assess how 90° ply thickness and placement influence damage initiation and growth, especially around the hole. To track damage progression, non-destructive ultrasonic inspections were carried out at predefined cycle intervals, enabling a direct comparison of the four laminate designs and potential performance gains.

The paper is organised into four main parts. Section 2 outlines the manufacturing process of the open-hole specimens. Section 3 details the experimental methodology, including the procedures and results for static and cyclic tensile testing as well as damage assessment. Finally, Section 4 presents the key conclusions and discusses potential directions for future research.

2 MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The open-hole tensile specimens used in this experimental programme were designed in accordance with the specifications provided in [10]. The central hole, located at the midpoint of both the specimen's length and width, was drilled and reamed following the recommendations of the standard to minimise any risk of damage in its vicinity. Since the presence of the hole generates an adequate stress concentration to induce failure, no additional tabs were employed.

Two stacking sequences were selected: [+45/−45/0/90]_{2S}, as recommended by the standard [10], and [+45/90/−45/0]_{2S}. For each stacking sequence, two laminate configurations were fabricated. The first consisted entirely of plies with conventional thickness (150 g/m²), while the second replaced the 90° plies with ultra-thin plies (50 g/m²), keeping all remaining plies at the conventional 150 g/m² grammage. This approach enabled a direct comparison between the two configurations without increasing the total ply count or manufacturing time.

The laminates were produced using TP 402/T700SC carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg supplied by North Thin Ply Technology and were cured using a standard autoclave process. The resulting four specimen types, along with their geometric parameters—length (L), width (w), thickness (t), and hole diameter (Ø=w/6)—are summarised in Table 1.

Specimens	L (mm)	w (mm)	ϕ (mm)	t (mm)	Stacking sequence	90° ply grammage (g/m ²)	0° and ±45° ply grammage (g/m ²)
OH.A	200	36	6	2.7	[+45/-45/0/90] _{2s}	150	150
OH.B				2.2		50	
OH.C				2.6	150		
OH.D				2.1	50		

Table 1: Dimensions of the specimens.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

3.1 Quasi-static tests

Quasi-static tensile tests were carried out to determine the tensile strength (σ_U) of the laminates. This value represents a key parameter for defining the load levels used later in cyclic testing. The strength values were computed based on the ultimate load and the gross cross-sectional area. For each of the four laminate configurations, five specimens were tested. Testing was performed using an Instron 4483 universal testing machine equipped with a 150 kN load cell.

The results, summarised in Table 2, include the mean σ_U for all specimen types, accompanied by their standard deviation and coefficient of variation. Overall, laminates incorporating ultra-thin 90° plies (OH.B and OH.D) exhibited higher tensile strength compared to those made exclusively with conventional plies. Additionally, the stacking sequence [+45/90/-45/0]_{2s} produced slightly higher strength values than the [+45/-45/0/90]_{2s} sequence.

Specimens	Stacking sequence	σ_U (MPa)	SD (MPa)	CV (%)
OH.A	[+45/-45/0/90] _{2s}	387.94	7.48	1.93
OH.B		446.74	6.10	1.36
OH.C	[+45/90/-45/0] _{2s}	415.29	24.52	5.90
OH.D		465.36	40.69	8.74

Table 2: Tensile strength (σ_U) for all specimen types.

3.1 Cyclic tests

The tensile fatigue performance of open-hole composite specimens was assessed through tension–tension (T–T) fatigue testing, conducted at a stress ratio of R=0.1. For each specimen configuration, the tensile strength (σ_U) was first determined to establish a baseline reference. The maximum applied stress for fatigue testing corresponded to 80% of the respective tensile strength for each configuration.

Four specimens from each configuration were tested under these conditions. All experiments were performed using an Instron 8801 universal dynamic testing machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell, operating at a loading frequency of 3 Hz.

Fatigue tests were periodically interrupted at predefined intervals—specifically, after 2,500; 5,000; 10,000; 20,000; 50,000; 75,000; 100,000; 150,000; and 200,000 load cycles—to evaluate the evolution of damage. At each interruption, ultrasonic inspection was employed to monitor damage initiation and propagation, facilitating comparative assessment of the different specimen configurations. The progression of damage is depicted for representative specimens in Figures 1 and 2, with OH.A and OH.B shown in Figure 1, and OH.C and OH.D in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Evolution of the extent of damage for laminates OH.A and OH.B.

Figure 2: Evolution of the extent of damage for laminates OH.C and OH.D.

Comparative analysis of OH.A and OH.B specimens highlights the beneficial role of incorporating ultra-thin 90° plies within the [+45/−45/0/90]_{2s} laminate. In OH.B specimens, free-edge damage was observed to initiate at a higher number of cycles relative to OH.A. Moreover, damage surrounding the open hole tended to manifest only after the free-edge damage had extended along the specimen free-edges, excluding the clamped regions. Consequently, the delayed onset of free-edge damage in OH.B specimens correspondingly postpones the initiation of hole-adjacent damage, effectively retarding the overall damage progression mechanism.

In the comparison shown in Figure 2 for specimens with the [+45/90/−45/0]_{2s} stacking sequence (OH.C and OH.D), a delay in the initiation of free-edge damage is again observed due to the inclusion of ultra-thin 90° plies. However, this delay does not influence the overall progression of damage. Beyond approximately 100,000 load cycles, the extent of free-edge damage becomes nearly identical in both specimen types. Furthermore, unlike the behaviour noted for the [+45/90/−45/0]_{2s} laminate, the delayed free-edge damage does not coincide with a postponed onset of damage around the hole. Consequently, the free-edge and open-hole damage mechanisms appear to evolve independently.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results indicate that substituting conventional 90° plies with ultra-thin plies in quasi-isotropic open-hole laminates enhances tensile fatigue performance for the [+45/−45/0/90]_{2s} configuration. The use of ultra-thin plies delays the progression of the damage mechanisms, highlighting their potential as a design feature for improving fatigue life. These findings underscore the suitability of ultra-thin 90° plies for quasi-isotropic laminates subjected to cyclic tensile loading and support their potential adoption in industrial applications.

In contrast, this benefit is not evident for the [+45/90/−45/0]_{2s} configuration. Although the initiation of free-edge and open-hole damage is postponed by incorporating ultra-thin 90° plies, the overall damage levels in both laminate types converge after extended cycling.

Future work will focus on refining the understanding of damage evolution in quasi-isotropic open-hole laminates through advanced inspection methods capable of resolving through-thickness damage localization. Such approaches will help clarify the contribution of ultra-thin plies to damage progression. Additionally, numerical modelling will be employed to optimise laminate design strategies incorporating ultra-thin plies.

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